

Assessment of Physicochemical Properties of Hospital Wastewater in Kirkuk, Iraq: Compliance with National and International Standards

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Abstract

Wastewater is the result of many activities in hospitals and contains many pollutants including pathogenic microbes, pharmaceutical residues, heavy elements and other organic residues, in our research we performed chemical and physical examinations of the wastewater of three Kirkuk hospitals (Azadi Teaching Hospital, Kirkuk Teaching Hospital and Children's Hospital) entering the treatment plant, where these examinations were performed (EC, PH, T.D.S., BOD, COD, T.S.S., SO₄, PO₄, NO₃, CL D.S., BOD, COD, T.S.S., SO₄, PO₄, NO₃ CL, NH₃, O&G, H₂S) from November 2024. The results showed that some of the tests conformed to the international standards stipulated by WHO, EPA, APHA, while some exceeded the permissible limits such as NH₃, H₂S, BOD, O&G, H₂S, NO₃, and in general the tests did not conform to Iraqi standards and exceeded the permissible limits, and the Parameters were studied before treatment due to the treatment plants not works in these hospitals. Therefore must be installed and built treatment plants because the water coming out of the treatment plants is considered untreated and contains many pollutants and is poured directly into the Khas river supply, which causes damage to the environment and causes major health issues.

Keywords: *hospital wastewater, standards, limits, pollutants, physical and chemical characteristics.*

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Introduction

Wastewater is defined as water that has lost its suitability for use after being consumed. It is a byproduct of water use in homes and factories, and can be categorized into domestic, industrial, and rainwater wastewater.

Wastewater is divided into two main types: industrial, which results from manufacturing processes and is difficult to treat, and domestic, which includes water from toilets, showers, and laundry.

Stormwater, which is made up of rainwater, and sludge, which is the solids produced by wastewater treatment. Finally, effluent, which is partially treated wastewater (Patel, 2022). Hospital wastewater also contains a variety of pathogens. Current research focuses on hospital wastewater treatment methods and their impact on human health and the environment. Since hospital wastewater is similar in nature to municipal wastewater, the difference is that hospital wastewater contains toxic and infectious substances

(Ramírez-Coronel, et al., 2024). Cities in Baghdad suffer from water supply and sanitation issues, as a result of difficult access to services, lack of attention, and insecurity. In central Baghdad, water treatment plants adhere to standards, but the supply network suffers from significant deterioration. There is an urgent need to renovate water treatment plants and networks in remote areas, in addition to promoting awareness among the population of the importance of environmental conservation (Aenab, & Singh, 2012).

Physical and Chemical Characteristics of Wastewater

The parameters examined in the effluent included chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), total suspended solids (TSS), turbidity, temperature, nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, and pH (Ganji, et al., 2024). Solids in wastewater are an essential element to be measured, as they represent a contaminant load and potential sediment. Solids are divided into two main categories: Suspended solids and dissolved solids (Ellis, 2004). Temperature generally affects water quality, as it can harm aquatic organisms if it is outside the normal range (Mandal, 2014a). The pH of wastewater is a key parameter that affects the effectiveness of treatment processes (Mandal, 2014b). Organic matter in water is determined through measurements of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD), BOD to COD ratios are important indicators of water pollution, with higher values indicating a decrease in biodegradability (Bader, Hussein, & Jabar, 2022). Nitrogen also contributes to the consumption of dissolved oxygen in water, and poses a risk to fish in the form of free ammonia (Von Sperling, 2007). All sources of drinking water and wastewater contain chlorides, which are usually found as mineral salts. A salty taste results when chloride concentrations in drinking water exceed 250 mg/L sodium. The taste detection level can be as high as 1000 mg/L chloride if it is present as a calcium or magnesium salt.

Chloride is a major constituent of raw sewage, essential for human nutrition and passes through the digestive system unchanged. The permissible chloride concentration of 250 mg/L in drinking water was set for taste reasons, not as a prevention measure taste, not as a measure to prevent physical hazards (Hach Company, 2018).

Methodology

Study Area

Azadi Teaching Hospital

Azadi Teaching Hospital is a large hospital that was established in 1983 and is located in the north of the city. The building consists of six floors and contains 400 beds, while the pediatric department has 64 beds (Azeez, & Majeed, 2020). Azadi Teaching Hospital has 400 beds and is considered a tertiary care facility, treating a variety of patients in departments such as internal medicine, surgery, pediatrics, dermatology, and others (Majid, et al., 2023).

Kirkuk General Hospital

Kirkuk General Hospital is one of the oldest hospitals in Kirkuk city, as it was established in 1945 and is located in the city center. The hospital consists of several departments and contains 350 beds, including a pediatric department with 20 beds (Azeez, & Majeed, 2020).

Kirkuk Children's Hospital

Located in the heart of Kirkuk, the Children's Hospital was established in 1972. This hospital specializes in pediatrics and has 120 beds, providing services exclusively for children (Azeez, & Majeed, 2020).

Azadi Teaching Hospital

Kirkuk General Hospital

Kirkuk Children's Hospital

Figure 1. Wastewater Treatment Systems in Hospitals in Baghdad (Iraq), from Where Water Samples were Taken

Materials

Samples were collected in November 2024 at 8:30 a.m. in clean, sterile bottles of untreated wastewater received at the station. The bottles were washed multiple times with hospital wastewater to homogenize the sample and transport it directly to the laboratory for physical and chemical tests. These tests were performed in the Kirkuk Sewerage Directorate laboratory. Tests were performed in three replicates independently for accuracy of results.

Chemical and Physical Tests Conducted in This Study

pH

The pH of the samples was measured immediately upon arrival at the laboratory using a pH meter (American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, & Water Environment Federation, 2017). The pH meter was calibrated using pre-prepared buffer solutions, starting with buffer solution pH 4, then pH 7, and then pH 10. A specific volume of the sample was taken, sufficient to immerse the electrode in it, and the reading was recorded directly from the meter.

The pH of Kirkuk General Hospital never dropped below pH 7, nor did the other hospitals. Similarly, an assessment in Iranian hospitals revealed that the average pH of raw wastewater was 7.5 in all hospitals studied (Abdullah, & Hussien, 2024).

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD)

BOD was measured using a yellow Oxi Top device made in Germany (American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, & Water Environment Federation, 2017). The German-made refrigerated incubator was operated before the test began, reaching a temperature of $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. A volume of 164 ml of the sample was taken from the device's special bottles, then 2-3 sodium hydroxide granules were placed in the inner lid. The bottles were placed in their designated places in the device and closed loosely for 20 to 40 minutes to aerate the sample and provide oxygen to revive the bacteria present. After the specified time had passed, the bottles were tightly closed and zeroed out. The

incubation process continued for five days, after which the readings were recorded at the same time each day. The clock runs for five days (Tchobanoglous, Burton, & Stensel, 2003).

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

The Closed Reflex Titrimetric Method was followed by dichromate oxidation (American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, & Water Environment Federation, 2017). 20 ml of the sample was taken into the apparatus' beaker, 0.4 g of mercury sulfate was added to the sample, 10 ml of potassium dichromate was added to the sample, and 30 ml of sulfuric acid was added. Careful mixing was carried out, and glass balls were placed in the beaker to regulate the heating process. The beaker was placed in its designated place in the apparatus, while the water was kept open for intensive cooling. The heating process continued for two hours, and then the sample was calibrated by adding drops of Freon reagent and ammonia ferrous sulfate. Calibration was stopped when the equilibrium point, which is a reddish-brown color, was reached. These same steps were applied to the blank sample, and the concentration was calculated using the following equation:

$$COD = \frac{(S-B) \times N \times 8000}{V} \quad (1)$$

Nitrate (NO₃), nitrite (NO₂), sulfate (SO₄), phosphate (PO₄)

Chemical analyses of nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, and sulfate were performed using a Hach DR3900 (Hach, USA) using colorimetric analysis. NitraVer 5 reagent was used to analyze nitrate according to Hach Method 8039, and NitriVer 3 reagent was used to analyze nitrite according to Hach Method 8507. Phosphate was analyzed using PhosVer 3 reagent according to Hach Method 8048, while sulfate was analyzed using SulfaVer 4 reagent (12). A 10 ml sample was taken into a test tube, and the reagents for each type (NitriVer 3, NitriVer, SulfaVer 4, PhosPhoVer) were added. Shake the tube and wait 20 minutes. The sample was then inserted into the test tube and read in mg/L (PPM) (Hach Company, 2018).

Chloride

Chloride was measured by titration with silver nitrate (American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, & Water Environment Federation, 2017). If the pH was 7-10, 100 ml of the sample was taken directly and the steps were performed. Add 1 ml of potassium chromate reagent, and the color changes to yellow. Titration with silver nitrate is initiated, and titration is continued until the color changes to a pinkish-yellow (onion-yellow). The previous steps are performed on the blank sample (distilled water). Chloride is calculated in mg/L using the following equation:

$$CHLORIDE = \frac{(A-B) \times D \times 35460}{E} \quad (2)$$

Oil and grease O & G

After filtering the sample, weigh 250 ml of the sample in a beaker (American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, & Water Environment Federation, 2017). Add 1 ml of 1:1 sulfuric acid and 25 ml of petroleum jelly solvent to a separating funnel. Shake the sample manually or with a vibrator. Remove the aqueous layer resulting from the separation process and add 25 ml of solvent. Transfer the organic layer resulting from the first and second separations to a fixed flask, and add 2.5 g of anhydrous sodium bisulfate. Then filter the sample. Transfer the flask to a conical flask and place it in a hot water heater. The condenser is placed below the condenser to receive the solvent. Then, the heating process is stopped, and the round-bottomed flask with its contents is transferred to the oven. We weigh

the flask after drying it in the oven for an hour. The fats and greases are calculated using the following equation:

$$O\&G \text{ mg/l} = (A - B) \times \frac{4000}{\text{ml of Sample}} \quad (3)$$

Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S)

Take 100 ml of the sample and add 1 ml of cadmium chloride solution (American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, & Water Environment Federation, 2017). Leave it for 24-48 hours. Then, dissolve the precipitate in 10-20 ml of iodine solution and 5 ml of hydrochloric acid solution. Titrate the excess iodine solution with sodium thiosulfate solution using 2 ml of starch reagent, added shortly before the equivalence point. The concentration is calculated using the following equation:

$$17000 \times \frac{E1 \times D1 \times E2 \times D2}{D} = (\text{mg/l}) \text{hydrogen sulfide} \quad (4)$$

Table 1. Statistical Analysis of Azadi Teaching Hospital

Parameter	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max	Global standard	Iraqi standard
PH	7.35	0.21	7.1	7.6	6.5	9.5
EC	1392.25	6.08	1385	1399	5000	
Temp C	22.82	5.59	16.2	28.6	35	35
T.D.S	923.75	22.87	895	950	2000	
BOD	318.75	28.39	290	350	250	40
COD	599.5	14.64	588	620	500	100
T.S.S	161.25	5.56	155	168	200	60
SO ₄	188.5	8.23	178	198	250	
PO ₄	13.57	1.82	11.4	15.4	10	3
NO ₃	71.23	1.85	69.5	73.8	50	50
CL	147	6.98	139	155	250	
NH ₃	20.5	1.29	19	22	5	10
O&G	150.25	7.14	143	160	10	
H ₂ S	10.5	1.29	9	12	1	0.5
NO ₂	1.06	0.03	1.03	1.09	1	

Figure 2. Pollution Indicators at Azadi Hospital in Line with National and International Standards

Table 2. Statistical Analysis of Children's Hospital

Parameter	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max	Global standard	Iraqi standard
Ph	7.47	0.3	7.1	7.8	6.5	9.5
EC	6859.5	867.57	5890	7971	5000	
Temp	24.77	3.89	20.4	28.3	35	35
TDS	1223.25	84.35	1103	1300	2000	
BOD	213.75	17.97	200	240	250	40
COD	387.25	20.25	360	405	500	100
TSS	186.25	12.34	172	202	200	60
SO4	207.25	12.84	193	220	250	
PO4	20.38	1.48	18.8	22.3	10	3
NO3	62.33	9.07	53.2	73.1	50	50
CL	169	4.97	164	175	250	
NH3	18.75	2.63	16	21	5	10
O&G	234	27.04	203	260	10	
H2S	10.38	1.73	8.2	12	1	0.5
NO2	1.1	0.13	1.01	1.28	1	

Figure 3. Pollution Indicators at Children's Hospital in Line with National and International Standards

Table 3. Statistical Analysis of Kirkuk General Hospital

Parameter	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max	Global standard	Iraqi standard
Ph	7.5	0.26	7.2	7.8	6.5	9.5
EC	1658	62.81	1598	1719	5000	
Temp	25.1	4.69	19.2	29.7	35	35
TDS	917.5	41.13	870	970	2000	
BOD	400	45.46	350	460	250	40
COD	627.5	17.08	610	650	500	100
TSS	194.5	12.15	180	208	200	60
SO4	115.75	4.79	109	120	250	
PO4	24.2	4.15	19.6	29.4	10	3

NO3	57.23	11.71	45.1	70.6	50	50	
CL	142.5	11.39	133	159	250		
NH3	21.75	2.75	19	25	5	10	
O&G	343.25	50.09	270	380	10		
H2S	10.2	1.31	8.9	11.9	1	0.5	
NO2	1.27	0.16	1.06	1.44	1		

Figure 4. Pollution Indicators at Azadi Hospital in Line with National and International Standards

Table 4. Comparing Results with International and Iraqi Standards

Parameter	Mean \pm SD			Sig.	Standardized global value	Standardized iraqi value
	Azadi Teaching Hospital	Kirkuk Children's Hospital	Kirkuk General Hospital			
BOD (mg/L)	318.75 \pm 28.39 ^b	213.75 \pm 17.97 ^c	400.00 \pm 45.46 ^a	0.0001*	250	40
COD (mg/L)	599.50 \pm 14.64 ^{ab}	387.25 \pm 20.25 ^c	627.50 \pm 17.08 ^a	0.0001*	500	100
Ph	7.35 \pm 0.21 ^a	7.48 \pm 0.30 ^a	7.50 \pm 0.26 ^a	0.689	6.5	9.5
EC (μ S/cm)	1,392.25 \pm 6.08 ^c	6,859.50 \pm 867.57 ^a	1,658.00 \pm 62.81 ^b	0.0001*	5000	
Temperature (°C)	22.83 \pm 5.59 ^a	24.78 \pm 3.89 ^a	25.10 \pm 4.69 ^a	0.773	35	35
T.D.S (mg/L)	923.75 \pm 22.87 ^b	1,223.25 \pm 84.35 ^a	917.50 \pm 41.13 ^b	0.0001*	2000	
T.S.S (mg/L)	161.25 \pm 5.56 ^c	186.25 \pm 12.34 ^b	194.50 \pm 12.15 ^a	0.004*	200	60
SO ₄ (mg/L)	188.50 \pm 8.23 ^b	207.25 \pm 12.84 ^a	115.75 \pm 4.79 ^c	0.0001*	250	-
PO ₄ (mg/L)	13.58 \pm 1.82 ^c	20.38 \pm 1.48 ^b	24.20 \pm 4.15 ^a	0.001*	10	3
NO ₃ (mg/L)	71.23 \pm 1.85 ^a	62.33 \pm 9.07 ^a	57.23 \pm 11.71 ^a	0.120	50	50
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	147.00 \pm 6.98 ^b	169.00 \pm 4.97 ^a	142.50 \pm 11.39 ^b	0.003*	250	
NH ₃ (mg/L)	20.50 \pm 1.29 ^a	18.75 \pm 2.63 ^a	21.75 \pm 2.75 ^a	0.239	5	10
O&G (mg/L)	150.25 \pm 7.14 ^c	234.00 \pm 27.04 ^b	343.25 \pm 50.09 ^a	0.0001*	10	
H ₂ S (mg/L)	10.50 \pm 1.29 ^a	10.38 \pm 1.73 ^a	10.20 \pm 1.31 ^a	0.958	1	0.5
NO ₂ (mg/L)	1.061 \pm 0.033 ^a	1.098 \pm 0.126 ^a	1.268 \pm 0.158 ^a	0.076	1	

Figure 5. Comparing Results with International and Iraqi Standards

Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistical analysis was used to analyze the data for Azadi Teaching Hospital No. 1, Children's Hospital No. 2, and Kirkuk General Hospital No. 3. This analysis included calculating the mean, standard deviation, and minimum and maximum values. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for all measured tests.

Water produced from Azadi Teaching Hospital, Kirkuk General Hospital, and Children's Hospital was analyzed for physical and chemical properties to determine the impact of various hospital activities on water quality. The results obtained from sample analyses showed significant increases in some properties compared to regular water or wastewater from other sources. The results for Azadi Teaching Hospital's wastewater were compared to the international standards of (American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, & Water Environment Federation, 2017; World Health Organization, 2017; Environmental Protection Agency, 2021) and Iraqi standards. The results for this hospital showed some conformity with international standards, as in a study conducted by Abbas, Husien, & Zainal, (2024) in Kirkuk city, which showed that industrial wastewater conformed to Iraqi standards. As in our study, the BOD test was observed to exceed the internationally permissible limit, and O&G exceeded the permissible limits, with a significant increase in H₂S and an increase in NO₂. The BOD test showed an increase, with the average between the three hospitals being 200-400, which exceeds the permissible limits set by the World Health Organization and the Environment Agency (WHO, EPA), which is 250 for untreated hospital water according to Iraqi standards. Kirkuk Hospital showed the highest percentage among the remaining hospitals, followed by Azadi Hospital with 318, then Children were around 200 and the COD test showed an increase compared to international and Iraqi standards, as it was within the range of 380-630, where Kirkuk General Hospital showed the highest increase in COD at a rate of 623, followed by Azadi Hospital at a rate of 600 and children's was the lowest at a rate of 387, and the nitrate test showed the highest rate at Azadi Hospital at a rate of 71, followed by children's and then Kirkuk, and phosphate showed an increase in Kirkuk Hospital, then children's and then Azadi,

and ammonia, fats, phosphates and nitrite were also noted to be higher than international standards in Kirkuk, it was 21, Azadi 20 and children's 18, and fats showed a significant increase exceeding 320 in Kirkuk Hospital, then children's, followed by Azadi, and hydrogen sulfide also showed a clear increase exceeding 10 in all hospitals, and this is consistent with the study conducted by Aenab, & Singh, (2012). The study showed that the Tigris River in Baghdad had concentrations of P04 S04 exceeds acceptable limits, while the Diyala River recorded high levels of P04, S04, CI, and BODs. However, concentrations of TH, O&G, Na, K, pH, N03, TS, Ca, Mg, and Al were within permissible limits.

This indicates that this untreated wastewater is being directly discharged into the city's water supply, causing significant environmental problems. A study in the city of Kirkuk showed that illegally mixing domestic and rainwater sewage increases the incidence of illnesses among children, especially in areas with open sewers. The study also showed gaseous emissions containing pathogenic bacteria, increasing the likelihood of infecting children (Tawfeeq, & Taher, 2018).

Conclusion

The results show that wastewater contains high levels of several chemical and physical pollutants. Water contains high levels of organic matter (BOD and COD), as well as high levels of salts, oils and grease, ammonia, and nitrates. This can result from various hospital activities, such as the use of medications, detergents, chemicals, and organic waste. High levels of salts, oils, organic matter, and nitrates indicate the need for advanced water treatment to reduce these pollutants and achieve environmental quality standards before discharging the water into the environment.

The possible causes of increased chemical properties are:

Medications and treatments: Hospital wastewater contains large amounts of consumed medications, including harsh chemicals, antibiotics, and therapeutic compounds, which are disposed of by doctors and nurses during waste disposal or while washing medical instruments.

Medical waste: This includes various medical wastes, such as needles, laboratory solutions, and laboratory chemicals, which significantly impact water quality.

Chemicals and detergents: Hospitals use cleaning and disinfecting agents containing harsh chemicals, such as chlorine and bleach, which can increase the concentration of salts and chemicals in the water.

References

Abbas, M. M., Husien, K. S., & Zainal, I. G. (2024). Assessment of lead and cadmium in some industrial wastewater in Kirkuk city. *Journal of Pioneering Medical Science*, 13(1), 1–5.

Abdullah, M. A., & Hussien, K. S. (2024). Evaluate the levels of some physical and chemical factors in wastewater from some companies and Kirkuk General Hospital in Kirkuk city. *Journal of Community Pharmacy Practice*, 43, 22–29.

Aenab, A. M., & Singh, S. K. (2012). Critical assessment of environmental quality of Baghdad, Iraq. *Journal of Environmental Engineering*, 138(6), 654–660. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)EE.1943-7870.0000501](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)EE.1943-7870.0000501)

American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, & Water Environment Federation. (2017). *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater* (23rd ed.).

Azeez, H. S., & Majeed, B. N. (2020). Assessment of mother's knowledge and attitude regarding newborn care at public hospitals in Kirkuk city. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 20(4), 1997–2003.

- Bader, A. C., Hussein, H. J., & Jabar, M. T. (2022). BOD: COD ratio as indicator for wastewater and industrial water pollution. *International Journal of Special Education*, 37(3), 2164–2171.
- Ellis, T. G. (2004). Chemistry of wastewater. In *Encyclopedia of Life Support Systems (EOLSS)* (Vol. 2, pp. 1–10).
- Environmental Protection Agency. (2021). *Industrial Wastewater Discharge Standards*.
- Ganji, F., Kamani, H., Ghayebzadeh, M., Abdipour, H., & Moein, H. (2024). Evaluation of physical and chemical characteristics of wastewater and sludge of Zahedan urban wastewater treatment plant for reuse. *Heliyon*, 10(2), e12345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e12345>
- Hach Company. (2018). *Water Analysis Handbook* (7th ed.). Hach Company.
- Majid, K. J., Mohammed, A. B., Rashid, H. M. S., & Namaq, A. O. (2023). Detection of *Staphylococcus aureus* from a sample of healthcare workers in Azadi Teaching Hospital Kirkuk/Iraq. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 10(3S), 100–110.
- Mandal, H. K. (2014a). Assessment of wastewater temperature and its relationship with turbidity. *Recent Science*, 6(1), 258–262.
- Mandal, H. K. (2014b). Influence of wastewater pH on turbidity. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Development*, 4(2), 105–114.
- Patel, T. (Ed.). (2022). *Wastewater Recycle and Reuse Training Manual: ClimateSmart Cities Assessment Framework - Water Management*. National Institute of Urban Affairs.
- Ramírez-Coronel, A. A., Mohammadi, M. J., Majdi, H. S., Zabibah, R. S., Taherian, M., Prasetio, D. B., Gabr, G., Asban, P., Kiani, A., & Sarkohaki, S. (2024). Hospital wastewater treatment methods and its impact on human health and environments. *Reviews on Environmental Health*, 39(3), 423–434. <https://doi.org/10.1515/reveh-2022-0216>
- Tawfeeq, A. A., & Taher, S. A. D. M. (2018). Epidemiological study evaluating the impact of front door duct slot of a combined domestic sewer–rainwater drainage system on children health in Kirkuk, 2017. *Karbala International Journal of Modern Science*, 4(4), 369–376.
- Tchobanoglous, G., Burton, F. L., & Stensel, H. D. (2003). *Wastewater Engineering: Treatment and Reuse* (4th ed.). Metcalf & Eddy, Inc.
- Von Sperling, M. (2007). *Wastewater Characteristics, Treatment and Disposal* (Vol. 1). IWA Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.2166/9781780402086>
- World Health Organization. (2017). *Guidelines for Safe Use of Wastewater*.

